

A STUDY OF PUNS USAGE IN LADY WINDERMERE'S FAN BY OSCAR WILDE

Marhabo Shokirova

Teacher, English language and literature faculty, Fersu

Toxirova Moxinur

Student, English language and literature faculty, Fersu

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11044561>

Abstract. This article explores the complex use of puns in Oscar Wilde's well-known drama "Lady Windermere's Fan." This paper explains how puns are used for humor, social commentary, and character development by looking at different wordplay examples. It demonstrates the subtle ways in which Wilde uses puns to enhance the play's themes and captivate the audience through language study and close reading.

Keywords: Lady Windermere's Fan, Oscar Wilde, wordplay, puns, comedy, and social critique.

Introduction. Renowned for his sharp mind and skill with words, Oscar Wilde skillfully employs puns in all of his writings to make readers laugh, think, and question accepted social mores. Puns are used liberally in "Lady Windermere's Fan," but they are more than just stylistic devices—puns are an essential part of the play's humor, thematic richness, and character development. The purpose of this essay is to investigate puns' significance in the play's setting by looking at their uses and ramifications.

1. Humor and Wit: The main purposes of puns in "Lady Windermere's Fan" are to produce humor and wit. Wordplay is a technique used by Wilde to make events humorous, ease stressful situations, and engage the audience. For instance, Lord Darlington's asides and double entendres highlight Wilde's wit and inventiveness while adding a humorous element to the dialogue. Puns are one of the ways that Wilde gives the play a playful charm that adds to its overall appeal [1].

2. Social Commentary: The play uses puns as a means of making social commentary in addition to their humorous effect. Using wordplay, Wilde attacks the superficiality and hypocrisy of Victorian society, especially its fixation on appearances and decorum. He challenges the audience to consider the principles and expectations that guide their own lives by exposing the inconsistencies and absurdities present in society norms through deft word choice [2].

The use of puns also aids in the character development of "Lady Windermere's Fan." Wordplay is a way for each character to express their individuality, morals, and worldview. For example, Lady Windermere's reluctance to parody emphasizes her sincerity and moral integrity, whereas Lord Darlington's fondness for clever repartee emphasizes his jaded cynicism [3]. Puns provide Wilde's characters more nuance and complexity in their interactions by shedding light on their inner motivations.

In conclusion, puns are more than just linguistic techniques in "Lady Windermere's Fan"; they are essential to the play's humor, social satire, and character growth. Wilde skillfully negotiates the complexity of Victorian society through wordplay, providing a sharp and clever critique of its customs and beliefs. Audiences may ensure the play's continued relevance and appeal by participating with the puns in order to obtain a deeper knowledge of the play's themes and characters.

References:

1. Wilde, Oscar. "Lady Windermere's Fan." Dover Publications, 1991.

2. Raby, Peter. "The Cambridge Companion to Oscar Wilde." Cambridge University Press, 1997.
3. Holland, Merlin. "The Complete Works of Oscar Wilde." HarperCollins, 2003.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY